

Data-Driven Intermittent Control of Linear Systems

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ABSTRACT

This paper is concerned with the data-driven intermittent control problem for unknown linear systems. By intermittent control, one refers to a controller that is activated during certain time intervals and deactivated otherwise. Based on the triggering methods of activation and deactivation, it can be categorized into time-based and event-based types. First, a data-driven time-based intermittent control (TbIC) framework is proposed for the scenario where the controller's activation and deactivation time sequences are aperiodic. Under this framework, the control gain can be directly solved from the noisy dataset. Subsequently, to eliminate unnecessary control intervals, an event-triggered mechanism from data is proposed to autonomously activate and deactivate the controller, based on which event-based intermittent control (EbIC) is further developed. Furthermore, TbIC and EbIC strategies with zero-order-hold updates are designed to reduce the number of controller updates during control intervals. Numerical examples demonstrate that, compared with the system-identification-based method, the proposed data-driven intermittent control is superior in terms of stability and control cost savings.

KEYWORDS

Data-driven control; intermittent control; event-triggered mechanism; noisy data

1. Introduction

Intermittent control, as a discontinuous control method, is characterized by applying control signals only within specific time intervals to achieve the desired control objectives, thus having the potential to save control costs. Thanks to this advantage of efficiently utilizing limited resources, intermittent control has shown broad application prospects in engineering fields such as spacecraft and vehicle control (Ong, Bahati, & Ames, 2022; Lei, Meng, Wang, Wang, & Sun, 2024; Liu, Ding, Zhang, & Xie, 2023; Mu & Wu, 2018). A typical example is the case of a spacecraft, which carries a finite amount of fuel and can only ignite its thrusters intermittently (Ong, Bahati, & Ames, 2022). Over the years, numerous studies on intermittent control have been conducted (Liu, Liu, & Li, 2021; Liu, Yang, Liu, & Hill, 2020; Wang, He, & Su, 2021; Yang, Ji, & Su, 2023; Liu, & Chen, 2015), predominantly adopting model-based methods that require a precise mathematical model of the system for controller design. How-

ever, obtaining an accurate model is often challenging or even infeasible in practice. Consequently, a critical research question arises: how can intermittent controllers be designed for dynamic systems with unknown models?

In recent years, data-driven control has emerged as a promising technique for designing controllers in model-free scenarios, leveraging data rather than explicit system models. A well-established approach within this paradigm is indirect data-driven control, which first identifies the system model from data and then applies classical model-based control design methods. Techniques such as maximum likelihood estimation, subspace methods, and neural network learning are commonly employed in system identification for this purpose (Ljung, 2010; Hou & Wang, 2013; Wang & Chen, 2006).

More recently, direct data-driven control has garnered significant attention (De Persis & Tesi, 2019; Van Waarde, Eising, Trentelman, & Camlibel, 2020; Bianchin, Vaquero, Cortes, & Dall’Anese, 2024; Li, Wang, Sun, Wang, & Chen, 2024; De Persis, Postoyan, & Tesi, 2024). Unlike the indirect approach, this method bypasses the system identification step and directly designs controllers using data generated from the unknown dynamic system. This approach not only avoids system identification errors but also requires less system-specific information in some scenarios (De Persis & Tesi, 2021; Van Waarde, Eising, Trentelman, & Camlibel, 2020; Kang & You, 2023). Due to these advantages, direct data-driven control has been successfully employed in a variety of control strategies, including state-feedback control, robust control, and finite-time control, effectively addressing stabilization challenges in linear systems (De Persis & Tesi, 2019; Van Waarde, Camlibel, & Mesbahi, 2022; Seuret & Tarbouriech, 2024; Li, Liu, & Liu, 2023; Miller, Zheng, Sznaier, & Hixenbaugh, 2024; Bianchi, Grammatico, & Cortes, 2025; Eising, Liu, Martinez, & Cortes, 2025; Dai & Sznaier, 2022). Notably, the above existing works adopt continuous control input signals, while direct data-driven intermittent control has received little attention, and such a research gap motivates our current study.

The design of intermittent control involves determining the intervals of control and non-control periods, as well as calculating the control gain. To date, numerous time-based intermittent control (TbIC) strategies have been developed, where controllers are activated or deactivated at predefined moments (Chen, Zhong, & Zheng, 2016). The strategy characterized by alternating fixed control intervals and fixed non-control intervals is referred to as periodic TbIC (P-TbIC) (Liu, Liu, & Li, 2021), where the time sequences of activation and deactivation exhibit periodic patterns; otherwise, it is called aperiodic TbIC (A-TbIC) (Liu, Yang, Liu, & Hill, 2020; Wang, He, & Su, 2021). In both cases, the control gain is related to the convergence and divergence rates of the system during the control and non-control intervals. It is noteworthy that these rates are normally characterized by utilizing information from the system matrices (Huang, Li, & Han, 2009). Consequently, a key challenge in data-driven TbIC lies in establishing a relationship between the intermittent control gain and the convergence or divergence rates directly from data, particularly in the absence of a precise mathematical model.

In some special scenarios, control resources are extremely scarce, thus requiring further energy savings, such as the inability to resupply energy for underwater unmanned vehicles conducting deep-sea exploration (Shi, Xie, Chen, Xing, & Zhang, 2024). To achieve this, event-based intermittent control (EbIC) (Ding, Wang, & Zhang, 2019; Ding & Wang, 2020; Yan, Liu, Xiao, & Zhang, 2022) has gained increasing attention. EbIC activates or deactivates the controller only when specific pre-defined events occur, avoiding unnecessary control actions caused by fixed startup sequences and

enabling more efficient resource utilization. However, existing event-triggered mechanisms (ETMs) for controller activation and deactivation typically rely on threshold parameters derived from system matrices. Transitioning from model-based EbIC to a data-driven version presents significant challenges, particularly in designing effective ETMs directly from data. The transition becomes even more complex when noise is present in the sampling process, further complicating the development of robust, data-driven solutions (Bisoffi, De Persis, & Tesi, 2022; Alanwar, Koch, Allgöwer, & Johansson, 2023).

Motivated by the discussions above, this paper intends to propose a direct data-driven intermittent control framework for dealing with the stabilization problem of unknown linear systems. The primary contributions of this paper are outlined below:

(1) The system's convergence and divergence rates are characterized from data, thereby deriving conditions for determining the intermittent control gains. Based on these conditions, a fundamental framework for direct data-driven intermittent control is established, with robustness to measurement noise.

(2) The relationship among the control interval, non-control interval, and control gain is revealed under noisy data for the TbIC scheme, and the corresponding data-based conditions for calculating the control gain are derived. This scheme applies to converting popular P-/A-TbIC strategies into data versions.

(3) A data-based ETM is developed, where the threshold parameter is computed directly from the data. This mechanism autonomously determines the activation and deactivation moments of the controller, effectively reducing unnecessary control actions.

(4) Stability criteria for the TbIC and EbIC strategies are derived based on data, leading to the development of a data-driven intermittent control framework with zero-order-hold updates. These approaches not only reduce control time but also decrease the frequency of input updates.

The remainder of this paper is summarized below. Section 2 presents the data-based intermittent control framework. Section 3 focuses on data-driven TbIC. The main results of the data-driven EbIC are provided in Section 4. Section 5 introduces TbIC and EbIC strategies with zero-order-hold updates. Section 6 draws the conclusions and discussions.

Notation: $\mathbb{R}^{p \times q}$ and \mathbb{R}^p denote the set of $p \times q$ real matrices and p dimensional Euclidean space. $\mathbb{R}_+ = [0, +\infty)$. $\mathbb{N} = \{0, 1, 2, \dots\}$. I_p and O_p denote the sets of $p \times p$ matrices with all elements being 1 and 0, respectively. For a real matrix S , the notation $S \succ (\succeq)0$ indicates that A is a symmetric positive (semi-)definite matrix, while $S \prec (\preceq)0$ denotes that S is a symmetric negative (semi-)definite matrix. $\lambda_M(S)$ and $\lambda_m(S)$ represent the maximum and minimum eigenvalues of matrix S , respectively.

2. Data-based framework

Consider a continuous-time linear system with dynamics described as

$$\dot{x}(t) = Ax(t) + Bu(t), \quad (1)$$

where $x(t) \in \mathbb{R}^p$ and $u(t) \in \mathbb{R}^q$ represent the state and control input. $A \in \mathbb{R}^{p \times p}$ and $B \in \mathbb{R}^{p \times q}$ are constant, unknown system matrices. (A, B) is assumed to be stabilizable.

Definition 2.1. The origin of system (1) is uniformly globally exponentially stable

(UGES) if there exist constants $a > 0$ and $b > 0$, independent of the initial time t_0 , such that for all initial states $x(t_0) \in \mathbb{R}^p$, the solution $x(t)$ satisfies:

$$\|x(t)\| \leq a\|x(t_0)\|e^{-b(t-t_0)}, \quad \forall t \geq t_0 \geq 0.$$

The main objective of this paper is to design intermittent state feedback controllers directly from noisy input-state data to stabilize the system (1) with unknown matrices A and B .

2.1. Noisy data pre-collection

We set the control input $u(t) \neq 0$ and conduct the second offline experiment on the following disturbed system

$$\dot{x}(t) = Ax(t) + Bu(t) + w(t), \quad (2)$$

where $\bar{w}(t) \in \mathbb{R}^p$ captures the unknown noise. Collect dataset $\mathbb{D} = \{\dot{x}(\varphi \cdot T_s), x(\varphi \cdot T_s), u(\varphi \cdot T_s)\}_{\varphi=0}^{L_s-1}$ at discrete time-instants $\{\varphi \cdot T_s\}_{\varphi=0}^{L_s-1}$, where T_s is a sampling time and $L_s > 0$ is the number of samples.

The collected data and disturbance sequence are organized into the following data matrices

$$\mathcal{X}_1 := [\dot{x}(0) \ \dot{x}(T_s) \ \dots \ \dot{x}((\varphi-1) \cdot T_s)] \in \mathbb{R}^{p \times L_s}, \quad (3a)$$

$$\mathcal{X}_0 := [x(0) \ x(T_s) \ \dots \ x((\varphi-1) \cdot T_s)] \in \mathbb{R}^{p \times L_s}, \quad (3b)$$

$$\mathcal{U} := [u(0) \ u(T_s) \ \dots \ u((\varphi-1) \cdot T_s)] \in \mathbb{R}^{q \times L_s}, \quad (3c)$$

$$\mathcal{W} := [w(0) \ w(T_s) \ \dots \ w((\varphi-1) \cdot T_s)] \in \mathbb{R}^{p \times L_s}, \quad (3d)$$

where \mathcal{X}_1 , \mathcal{X}_0 and \mathcal{U} are available, and \mathcal{W} is unknown. To ensure the richness of the collected data \mathbb{D} , we assume the following condition.

Assumption 1. The matrix $[\mathcal{U}; \mathcal{X}_0]$ has full row rank.

To facilitate the subsequent analysis, the following matrices and lemmas are given.

$$\mathcal{Z} := [\mathcal{U}^T \ \mathcal{X}_0^T], \quad \Pi := (\mathcal{Z}^T \mathcal{Z})^{-1}, \quad \mathbb{I} := \begin{bmatrix} I_{q \times q} \\ O_{p \times p} \end{bmatrix}. \quad (4)$$

Lemma 1. (De Persis, Postoyan, & Tesi, 2024) Let Assumption 1 hold, for any matrix $K \in \mathbb{R}^{p \times q}$, there exists a matrix $G \in \mathbb{R}^{L_s \times p}$ such that

$$\begin{bmatrix} K \\ I_p \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathcal{U} \\ \mathcal{X}_0 \end{bmatrix} G, \quad (5)$$

which implies that

$$A + BK = (\mathcal{X}_1 - \mathcal{W})G.$$

Lemma 2. Let Assumption 1 hold, for any matrix $K \in \mathbb{R}^{p \times q}$, there exists a matrix $L \in \mathbb{R}^{L_s \times p}$ such that

$$\begin{bmatrix} K \\ O_p \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathcal{U} \\ \mathcal{X}_0 \end{bmatrix} L, \quad (6)$$

which implies that

$$BK = (\mathcal{X}_1 - \mathcal{W})L.$$

We assume that the noisy $w(t)$ is bounded, this assumption is found in some existing works (De Persis & Tesi, 2019; De Persis, Postoyan, & Tesi, 2024; Alanwar, Koch, Allgöwer, & Johansson, 2023).

Assumption 2. $\mathcal{W} \in \mathbb{W}$, where

$$\mathbb{W} := \{W \in \mathbb{R}^{p \times s} : WW^T \leq \Theta\Theta^T\}, \quad (7)$$

and $\Theta \in \mathbb{R}^{p \times s}$ is a known matrix.

To facilitate the subsequent analysis, the following lemmas are given.

Lemma 3. (De Persis, Postoyan, & Tesi, 2024) Let $S \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times p}$ be given matrices. Then for any $\epsilon > 0$ and any $W \in \mathbb{W}$ with \mathbb{W} in (7), we have

$$SW^T + WS^T \leq \epsilon^{-1}SS^T + \epsilon\Theta\Theta^T.$$

2.2. Data-driven intermittent controller design

We first develop a data-driven intermittent control framework for the system (1). Hence, to characterize the intermittent control, the time interval $[0, +\infty)$ is divided into $[t_\sigma, t_\sigma + \Delta_\sigma) \cup [t_\sigma + \Delta_\sigma, t_{\sigma+1})$ where $\sigma \in \mathbb{N}$, $[t_\sigma, t_\sigma + \Delta_\sigma)$ and $[t_\sigma + \Delta_\sigma, t_{\sigma+1})$ are control and non-control intervals, respectively. Then, the controller can be given as

$$u(t) = \begin{cases} Kx(t), & t \in [t_\sigma, t_\sigma + \Delta_\sigma), \\ 0, & t \in [t_\sigma + \Delta_\sigma, t_{\sigma+1}), \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

where $\{t_\sigma\}_{\sigma=0}^\infty$ is the sequence of control starting moments, $t_0 = 0 < t_1 < \dots < t_\sigma \dots$ and $\lim_{\sigma \rightarrow \infty} t_\sigma = +\infty$, $0 \leq \Delta_\sigma \leq t_{\sigma+1} - t_\sigma$ is the control length of σ th interval. The control gain is of the following form

$$K = \mathcal{U}\Phi(\mathcal{X}_0\Phi)^{-1} \in \mathbb{R}^{q \times p}, \quad (9)$$

where Φ is a matrix computed from the dataset (3), and is specified later. The structure of (9) originates from the block matrix $K = \mathcal{U}G$ of (5). In addition, we set $L = \mathcal{Z}\Pi\Pi\Pi K$.

Applying the controller (8) to the system (1) yields

$$\begin{cases} \dot{x}(t) = Ax(t) + BKx(t), & t \in [t_\sigma, t_\sigma + \Delta_\sigma), \\ \dot{x}(t) = Ax(t), & t \in [t_\sigma + \Delta_\sigma, t_{\sigma+1}). \end{cases} \quad (10a)$$

$$(10b)$$

It can be seen from (10) that finding Φ is the key to calculating the intermittent control gain K . Next, we will establish conditions for determining Φ based on noisy data for different controller activation and deactivation strategies. In Sections 3 and 4, we will study data-driven TbIC and EbIC strategies, respectively. Furthermore, we discuss the data-driven TbIC and EbIC with zero-order-hold updates in Section 5.

3. Data-driven time-based intermittent control

In this section, we will investigate the stability of system (1) under the data-based TbIC strategy, where the control starting sequence $\{t_\sigma\}_{\sigma=0}^\infty$ and control interval length Δ_σ are manually set. We will derive data-driven stability conditions under A-TbIC and calculate the corresponding feedback gain matrix K from dataset (3). This method is applicable to different types of A-TbIC and equally applicable to P-TbIC. A-TbIC strategies are generally based on the following assumptions regarding controlled intervals and uncontrolled intervals, which are widely used in existing studies, such as (Wang, He, & Su, 2021) and (Wu, Guo, Xue, Ahn, & Liu, 2024; Wu, Wang, Liu, & Xu, 2021).

Assumption 3. For the A-TbIC strategy, there exist $\theta \in (0, 1)$ and $\pi \geq 0$ such that

$$\theta(t - s) - \pi \leq F_c(t, s), \quad \forall t > s > t_0$$

where $F_c(t, s)$ represents the total control interval length on the time interval $[s, t]$, θ denotes the average control rate, and π is called the elasticity number. $F_c + F_r = t - s$, where F_r denotes the total rest time on the time interval $[s, t]$.

Assumption 4. For the A-TbIC strategy, there exist two positive scalars $0 < \bar{\Delta} < \varpi < +\infty$ such that, for $\sigma \in \mathbb{N}$,

$$\inf_{\sigma} \Delta_\sigma = \bar{\Delta}, \quad \sup_{\sigma} (t_{\sigma+1} - t_\sigma) = \varpi.$$

It can be seen that Assumptions 3 and 4 are constraints on the control subinterval (Liu, & Chen, 2015; Ni, Wang, Huang, Ma, & Shen, 2022; Yu, Jiang, & Hu, 2017) and the total control interval (Wang, He, & Su, 2021; Wu, Guo, Xue, Ahn, & Liu, 2024; Wu, Wang, Liu, & Xu, 2021), respectively. Next, we present stability results under assumption 3, with analogous results obtainable under assumption 4. This demonstrates the applicability of our framework to existing TbIC results.

Theorem 1. Consider the linear system (1). Suppose Assumptions 1-3 hold. If there exist matrix Φ , and positive scalars $\alpha, \beta, \varepsilon$ such that

$$\begin{bmatrix} \hat{\Xi} & \Phi^T \\ \Phi & -\varepsilon I \end{bmatrix} \prec 0, \quad (11a)$$

$$\mathcal{X}_0 \Phi \succ 0, \quad (11b)$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} \check{\Xi} & \Phi^T \\ \Phi & -\varepsilon(1 + \lambda_z^{-1})I \end{bmatrix} \prec 0, \quad (11c)$$

and

$$\alpha\theta - \beta(1 - \theta) > 0, \quad (12)$$

where $\hat{\Xi} = \mathcal{X}_1\Phi + (\mathcal{X}_1\Phi)^T + \alpha\mathcal{X}_0\Phi + \varepsilon\Theta\Theta^T$, $\tilde{\Xi} = \mathcal{X}_1\Phi + (\mathcal{X}_1\Phi)^T - \Upsilon\Phi - (\Upsilon\Phi)^T - \beta\mathcal{X}_0\Phi + 2\varepsilon\Theta\Theta^T$, $\Upsilon = \mathcal{X}_1\tilde{\Upsilon}$ with $\tilde{\Upsilon} = Z\Pi\mathbb{I}U$, and $\lambda_z = \lambda_M(\tilde{\Upsilon}^T\tilde{\Upsilon})$. Then, the origin of system (1) is UGES under the aperiodic intermittent controller (8)-(9).

Proof: Let $G := \Phi P$ and $P := (\mathcal{X}_0\Phi)^{-1}$. Consider the Lyapunov function $V(x) = x^T P x$, where P is symmetric positive definite matrix due to (11b). We will develop the stability analysis of the system (1) based on the data-based conditions (11) from the control and non-control intervals respectively.

(i) In this part, we will analyze the variation of the Lyapunov function in the control intervals.

According to the Schur complement, (11a) is equivalent to

$$\mathcal{X}_1\Phi + (\mathcal{X}_1\Phi)^T + \alpha\mathcal{X}_0\Phi + \varepsilon^{-1}\Phi^T\Phi + \varepsilon\Theta\Theta^T \prec 0. \quad (13)$$

By applying Lemma 3 with $S = -\Phi^T$ to (13), we obtain

$$(\mathcal{X}_1 - \mathcal{W})\Phi + [(\mathcal{X}_1 - \mathcal{W})\Phi]^T \prec -\alpha\mathcal{X}_0\Phi. \quad (14)$$

Since (11b) and $G = \Phi P$, it follows from (14) that

$$(\mathcal{X}_1 - \mathcal{W})GP^{-1} + P^{-1}[(\mathcal{X}_1 - \mathcal{W})G]^T \prec -\alpha P^{-1}. \quad (15)$$

Note that $\mathcal{X}_0G = I_p$ and $K = \mathcal{U}\Phi(\mathcal{X}_0\Phi)^{-1}$ can also be written as $K = \mathcal{U}G$. According to Lemma 2, we have $A + BK = (\mathcal{X}_1 - \mathcal{W})G$. By pre- and post-multiplying (15) with matrix P , it can be derived that

$$\begin{aligned} P(\mathcal{X}_1 - \mathcal{W})G + [(\mathcal{X}_1 - \mathcal{W})G]^T P &\prec -\alpha P, \\ P(A + BK) + (A + BK)^T P &\prec -\alpha P, \\ PA + A^T P + PBK + (BK)^T P &\prec -\alpha P. \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

When $t_\sigma \leq t < t_\sigma + \Delta_\sigma$, we differentiate $V(x)$ along the system (10a) and obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{V}(x) &= x^T [P(A + BK) + (A + BK)^T P] x \\ &\leq -\alpha x^T P x = -\alpha V(x), \end{aligned}$$

due to (16).

Thus, for $\forall t \in [t_\sigma, t_\sigma + \Delta_\sigma)$, we have

$$V(x(t)) \leq V(x(t_\sigma))e^{-\alpha(t-t_\sigma)}. \quad (17)$$

(ii) In this part, we will analyze the variation of the Lyapunov function in the non-control intervals.

Based on (2) and (3), we have $\mathcal{X}_1 - \mathcal{W} = A\mathcal{X}_0 + B\mathcal{U} = [B \ A]\mathcal{Z}^T$. Then, by (4) and (9), we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} (\mathcal{X}_1 - \mathcal{W})L &= [B \ A]\mathcal{Z}^T \mathcal{Z}\Pi\Pi\mathcal{U}\Phi(\mathcal{X}_0\Phi)^{-1} \\ &= BK. \end{aligned} \quad (18)$$

Based on the Schur complement, (11c) is equivalent to

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{X}_1\Phi + (\mathcal{X}_1\Phi)^T + \varepsilon^{-1}\Phi^T\Phi + \varepsilon\Theta\Theta^T - [\Upsilon\Phi + (\Upsilon\Phi)^T] \\ + \varepsilon^{-1}\Phi^T\tilde{\Upsilon}^T\tilde{\Upsilon}\Phi + \varepsilon\Theta\Theta^T \prec \beta\mathcal{X}_0\Phi. \end{aligned} \quad (19)$$

Applying Lemma 3 with $Y = \Phi^T$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} -\Upsilon\Phi - (\Upsilon\Phi)^T + \varepsilon^{-1}\Phi^T\tilde{\Upsilon}^T\tilde{\Upsilon}\Phi + \varepsilon\Theta\Theta^T \\ \succeq -\Upsilon\Phi - (\Upsilon\Phi)^T + \mathcal{W}\tilde{\Upsilon}\Phi + (\mathcal{W}\tilde{\Upsilon}\Phi)^T \\ = -(\mathcal{X}_1 - \mathcal{W})\tilde{\Upsilon}\Phi - [(\mathcal{X}_1 - \mathcal{W})\tilde{\Upsilon}\Phi]^T. \end{aligned} \quad (20)$$

Similar to (16), combining (18) and (20), we can derive from (19) that

$$\begin{aligned} (\mathcal{X}_1 - \mathcal{W})\Phi + [(\mathcal{X}_1 - \mathcal{W})\Phi]^T - (\mathcal{X}_1 - \mathcal{W})\tilde{\Upsilon}\Phi \\ - [(\mathcal{X}_1 - \mathcal{W})\tilde{\Upsilon}\Phi]^T \prec \beta\mathcal{X}_0\Phi, \\ P(A + BK) + (A + BK)^T P - \\ PBK - (BK)^T P \prec \beta P, \\ PA + A^T P \prec \beta P. \end{aligned} \quad (21)$$

When $t_\sigma + \Delta_\sigma \leq t < t_{\sigma+1}$, differentiating $V(x)$ along the system (10b) and combining with (21), one obtains

$$\dot{V}(x) = x^T(PA + A^T P)x \leq \beta x^T P x = \beta V(x).$$

Then, for $\forall t \in [t_\sigma + \Delta_\sigma, t_{\sigma+1})$, we have

$$V(x(t)) \leq V(x(t_\sigma + \Delta_\sigma))e^{\beta(t - t_\sigma - \Delta_\sigma)}. \quad (22)$$

From (17) of part (i) and (22) of part (ii), when $t \in [t_\sigma, t_\sigma + \Delta_\sigma)$, one has

$$\begin{aligned} V(x(t)) \leq V(x(t_0)) \exp[-\alpha \sum_{q=0}^{\sigma-1} \Delta_q + \beta \sum_{q=0}^{\sigma-1} (t_{q+1} - t_q \\ - \Delta_q) - \alpha(t - t_\sigma)]. \end{aligned} \quad (23)$$

Meanwhile, when $t \in [t_\sigma + \Delta_\sigma, t_{\sigma+1})$, we can gain

$$\begin{aligned} V(x(t)) \leq V(x(t_0)) \exp[-\alpha \sum_{q=0}^{\sigma-1} \Delta_q + \beta \sum_{q=0}^{\sigma-1} (t_{q+1} \\ - t_q - \Delta_q) - \alpha\Delta_\sigma + \beta(t - t_\sigma - \Delta_\sigma)]. \end{aligned} \quad (24)$$

Based on Assumption 3, it follows from (23) and (24) that for any $t > 0$

$$\begin{aligned} V(x(t)) &\leq V(x(t_0))e^{-\alpha F_c(0,t)+\beta F_r(0,t)} \\ &\leq V(x(t_0))e^{-\alpha(\theta t-\pi)+\beta((1-\theta)t+\pi)} \\ &\leq V(x(t_0))e^{(-\alpha\theta t+\beta(1-\theta))t+(\alpha+\beta)\pi}. \end{aligned}$$

According to (12), we can get

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \kappa \|x(t_0)\| e^{\frac{1}{2}[(-\alpha\theta+\beta(1-\theta))t+(\alpha+\beta)\pi]} = 0,$$

where $t_0 = 0$ is the first element of the sequence $\{t_\sigma\}_{\sigma=0}^\infty$ and $\kappa = \lambda_M(P)/\lambda_m(P)$. Therefore, the origin of system (1) is UGES under data-driven A-TbIC (8) with feedback gain K computed from (11) and (12). \square

Remark 1. Compared to existing data-driven control methods with continuous inputs (De Persis & Tesi, 2019; Van Waarde, Camlibel, & Mesbahi, 2022; Seuret & Tarbouriech, 2024; Li, Liu, & Liu, 2023), this paper is one of the earliest attempts to develop an intermittent control approach for stabilizing unknown systems, offering a potential way to reduce control costs under a data-driven framework. The key difficulty lies in solving the control gain K , which is related not only to the convergence rate of the system in the control interval, but also to the divergence rate in the non-control interval (i.e., $\|x(t)\| \leq \kappa \|x(t_0)\| e^{-\alpha t/2}$ and $\|x(t)\| \leq \kappa \|x(t_0)\| e^{\beta t/2}$). The combined effect of Lemma 1 and Lemma 2 provides a characterization method for the divergence rate (11c) based on the dataset (3). As a result, (9) and (11) establish a data-based framework for solving the variation rates α , β , and the corresponding control gain K .

Remark 2. If $t_\sigma = \sigma\Pi$ and $\Delta_\sigma = \Delta$, where $\Pi > 0$ and $\Delta \in (0, \Pi)$, then (9) will become a periodic intermittent controller. At this point, it is sufficient to replace condition (12) with $\alpha\Delta - \beta(\Pi - \Delta) > 0$, and Theorem 1 will degenerate into the P-TbIC result. Moreover, concerning Assumption 4 on the constraints for each interval in (Ni, Wang, Huang, Ma, & Shen, 2022) and (Yu, Jiang, & Hu, 2017), Theorem 4 remains valid by replacing the condition (13) with $\alpha\bar{\Delta} - \beta(\varpi - \bar{\Delta}) > 0$. Therefore, the proposed data-driven framework is applicable to the currently popular TbIC.

Next, we will verify the theoretical result of Theorem 1 using an example and compare it with the system-identification-based TbIC method.

Example 1: Consider the linear system (1) with system matrices

$$A = \begin{bmatrix} 0.3567 & 0.3357 & 1.8710 & 0.2019 \\ 1.8141 & -1.2806 & 1.5833 & -0.4675 \\ -1.2931 & -0.3107 & -0.6744 & 0.5776 \\ 0.8440 & 0.3750 & 1.6486 & -0.6796 \end{bmatrix},$$

$$B = [-0.1241 \quad 1.4897 \quad 1.4090 \quad 1.4172]^T.$$

Assume that the matrices A and B are unknown. Based on the disturbed system (2) with $\Theta = 0.01\sqrt{L_s}I$, two offline experiments are conducted to collect the dataset (3), respectively. In both experiments, the initial state and the control input are randomly selected within the interval $[-1, 1]$, the sampling time $T_s = 0.1$, and the sampling number $L_s = 20$, satisfying Assumptions 1 and 2. The control intervals for intermittent

controller (8) are $\cup_{\sigma=0}^{\infty}([2\sigma, 2\sigma+0.1) \cup [2\sigma+0.78, 2\sigma+1.3))$, which satisfies Assumption 4 that $\theta = 0.48$ and $\pi = 0.05$.

Case 1 (Data-driven TbIC): We design the control gain K based on the result of Theorem 1. The parameters are $\alpha_1 = 0.5$ and $\beta_1 = 0.1$. Solving the data-based conditions (11) and (12) using CVX of Matlab to obtain the feedback gain matrix $K = [-4.6934, -0.1435, -5.3410, -10.3210]$.

Case 2 (System-identification-based TbIC): Based on the above dataset $\mathbb{D} = \{\dot{x}(\varphi \cdot T_s), x(\varphi \cdot T_s), u(\varphi \cdot T_s)\}_{\varphi=0}^{19}$, we estimate the system matrices using the N4SID function of MATLAB. The relative errors of the estimated A_s and B_s matrices are 6.6% and 12.0%, respectively. To ensure the accuracy of the identification, we added data to 60, resulting in relative errors of 4.4% and 4.5%, respectively. The identified matrices are as

$$A_s = \begin{bmatrix} 0.2641 & 0.3855 & 1.8636 & 0.1610 \\ 1.7747 & -1.2370 & 1.6475 & -0.4999 \\ -1.2713 & -0.3715 & -0.7105 & 0.5972 \\ 0.7902 & 0.4328 & 1.6736 & -0.7181 \end{bmatrix},$$

$$B_s = [-0.1870 \quad 1.4712 \quad 1.4753 \quad 1.3533]^T.$$

Based on the above matrices, we solve for parameter P using conditions (12), (16), and (21), where $K = -B_s^T P$, and then design the control gain $K = [-1.5619, -1.7128, 0.3038, -5.2797]$.

The trajectories $x(t)$ of the two methods are shown in Figure 1. It can be seen that under direct data-driven TbIC, the system is stable for 8 seconds, while the method based on system identification is stable for 14 seconds. The control costs $\int_0^{20} u^T(t)u(t)dt$ of the two methods are 6.5923×10^4 and 2.7710×10^5 , respectively. This indicates that the method we propose has a faster convergence speed and lower control costs. In particular, we avoid computationally complex identification processes.

Figure 1. Trajectories $x(t)$ of the system (1) under two cases

4. Data-driven event-based intermittent control

Unlike TbIC in Section 3, the EbIC strategy does not require the pre-designed control intervals $[t_\sigma, t_\sigma + \Delta_\sigma)$ and the non-control intervals $[t_\sigma + \Delta_\sigma, t_{\sigma+1})$, but rather is based on events, which can further reduce the control time. For the sake of notational simplicity, we define $s_\sigma := t_\sigma + \Delta_\sigma$.

The activation and deactivation time sequences $\{t_\sigma\}_{\sigma=0}^\infty, \{s_\sigma\}_{\sigma=0}^\infty$ of the intermittent controller (8) will be determined by the following ETM consisting of the state $x(t)$ and the measurement datasets (3):

$$s_\sigma = \inf \{t \mid t > t_\sigma, x^T(t)(\mathcal{X}_0\Phi)^{-1}x(t) < \omega(t)\}, \quad (25)$$

$$t_{\sigma+1} = \inf \{t \mid t > s_\sigma, x^T(t)(\mathcal{X}_0\Phi)^{-1}x(t) > \xi(t)\}. \quad (26)$$

Here, $\xi(t)$ and $\omega(t)$ are dynamic threshold parameters that evolve according to

$$\dot{\xi}(t) = -\eta\xi(t), \xi(0) = \gamma_1 x^T(0)(\mathcal{X}_0\Phi)^{-1}x(0), \quad (27)$$

$$\dot{\omega}(t) = -\eta\omega(t), \omega(0) = \gamma_2 x^T(0)(\mathcal{X}_0\Phi)^{-1}x(0), \quad (28)$$

where constants $\eta > 0, \gamma_1 > 1, 0 < \gamma_2 < \gamma_1$, and Φ will be given later.

Based on ETM (25)-(26), it can be ensured that the linear system (1) is UGES, while Zeno behavior is effectively avoided, as demonstrated in the following theorem.

Theorem 2. Consider the linear system (1). Suppose Assumptions 1-2 hold. If there exist matrix Φ , and positive scalars $\alpha > \eta, \beta, \varepsilon$ such that (11) holds. Then, the origin of system (1) is UGES under the intermittent controller (8)-(9) and data-based ETM (25)-(26). Additionally, Zeno behavior is excluded, with the minimum inter-event time satisfying

$$t_{\sigma+1} - t_\sigma \geq \frac{\ln(\gamma_1) - \ln(\gamma_2)}{\eta + \beta}.$$

Proof: We will prove this in two steps. The first step is confirming the absence of Zeno behavior, and the second step is proving the stability of the system (1).

Step 1: In the first step, we guarantee that Zeno does not exist by proving the boundedness of the control and non-control intervals.

Based on conditions (11), we have $P = (\mathcal{X}_0\Phi)^{-1} > 0$. Then, the data-based ETM (25)-(26) can be rewritten as

$$s_\sigma = \inf \{t \mid t > t_\sigma, x^T(t)Px(t) < \omega(t)\}, \quad (29)$$

$$t_{\sigma+1} = \inf \{t \mid t > s_\sigma, x^T(t)Px(t) > \xi(t)\}. \quad (30)$$

Similarly, Eqs. (27)-(28) can be rewritten as $\xi(0) = \gamma_1 x^T(0)Px(0)$ and $\omega(0) = \gamma_2 x^T(0)Px(0)$. According to (29) and (30), we have that system (1) satisfies $x^T(t)Px(t) \geq \omega(t)$ when $[t_\sigma, s_\sigma)$, and $x^T(t)Px(t) \leq \xi(t)$ when $[s_\sigma, t_{\sigma+1})$.

(i) In this part, we will discuss the boundedness of the control intervals.

For $t \in [t_\sigma, s_\sigma)$, the controller defined in (8) is activated. It follows from the ETM (29) and (30) that

$$x^T(t_\sigma)Px(t_\sigma) = \xi(t_\sigma), \quad (31)$$

with $\xi(t_\sigma) = \gamma_1 V(0) e^{-\eta t_\sigma}$.

Similar to the part (i) of Theorem 1, it is easy to obtain

$$\begin{aligned} V(x(t)) &\leq e^{-\alpha(t-t_\sigma)} V(x(t_\sigma)) \\ &\leq e^{-\alpha(t-t_\sigma) - \eta t_\sigma} \gamma_1 V(x(0)). \end{aligned}$$

Then, when $t = s_\sigma$, we have

$$V(x(s_\sigma)) = \omega(s_\sigma) \leq e^{-\alpha(s_\sigma - t_\sigma) - \eta t_\sigma} \gamma_1 V(x(0)).$$

From (28) and $\omega(s_\sigma) = e^{-\eta s_\sigma} \gamma_2 V(x(0))$, we obtain the following inequality

$$e^{-\eta s_\sigma} \gamma_2 V(x(0)) \leq e^{-\alpha(s_\sigma - t_\sigma) - \eta t_\sigma} \gamma_1 V(x(0)),$$

which is equivalent to

$$e^{-\eta(s_\sigma - t_\sigma)} \gamma_2 V(x(0)) \leq e^{-\alpha(s_\sigma - t_\sigma)} \gamma_1 V(x(0)).$$

This implies that

$$s_\sigma - t_\sigma \leq \frac{\ln(\gamma_1) - \ln(\gamma_2)}{\alpha - \eta}. \quad (32)$$

(ii) In this part, we will discuss the boundedness of the non-control intervals.

For $t \in [s_\sigma, t_{\sigma+1})$, the system (1) is performed without the control input. Based on the ETM (29), $V(x(s_\sigma)) = \omega(s_\sigma) = \gamma_2 V(0) e^{-\eta s_\sigma}$.

Similar to the part (ii) of Theorem 1, $V(x(t))$ can further be obtained as

$$V(x(t)) \leq e^{\beta(t-s_\sigma) - \eta s_\sigma} \gamma_2 V(x(0)). \quad (33)$$

For the next moment $t_{\sigma+1}$, the ETM (30) is triggered and the controller is activated, and then one has

$$V(x(t_{\sigma+1})) = \xi(t_{\sigma+1}) \leq e^{\beta(t_{\sigma+1} - s_\sigma) - \eta s_\sigma} \gamma_2 V(x(0)).$$

Since $\xi(t_{\sigma+1}) = e^{-\eta t_{\sigma+1}} \gamma_1 V(x(0))$, one has

$$\begin{aligned} e^{-\eta t_{\sigma+1}} \gamma_1 V(x(0)) &\leq e^{\beta(t_{\sigma+1} - s_\sigma) - \eta s_\sigma} \gamma_2 V(x(0)), \\ e^{-(\eta + \beta)(t_{\sigma+1} - s_\sigma)} \gamma_1 V(x(0)) &\leq \gamma_2 V(x(0)), \end{aligned}$$

and yields

$$t_{\sigma+1} - s_\sigma \geq \frac{\ln(\gamma_1) - \ln(\gamma_2)}{\eta + \beta}. \quad (34)$$

As the non-control interval has a lower bound, controller does not switch infinitely for a finite time.

Step 2: In the second step, we will show that the origin of system (1) is UGES under the EbIC (8) with data-based ETM (25)-(26).

The Lyapunov function used in Theorem 1 is considered here as well. Based on the auxiliary functions (27) and (28), we obtain $\xi(t) \leq \gamma_1 V(x(0))e^{-\eta t}$ and $\omega(t) \leq \gamma_2 V(x(0))e^{-\eta t}$. The variation of the $V(x(t))$ can be divided into the following three regions:

$$\begin{aligned}\aleph_1(t) &:= \left\{ \nu \in \mathbb{R}_+ \mid \nu \geq \gamma_1 V(x(0))e^{-\eta(t-t_0)} \right\}, \\ \aleph_2(t) &:= \left\{ \nu \in \mathbb{R}_+ \mid \nu < \gamma_2 V(x(0))e^{-\eta(t-t_0)} \right\}, \\ \aleph_3(t) &:= \left\{ \nu \in \mathbb{R}_+ \mid \gamma_2 V(x(0))e^{-\eta(t-t_0)} \right. \\ &\quad \left. \leq \nu < \gamma_1 V(x(0))e^{-\eta(t-t_0)} \right\}.\end{aligned}\tag{35}$$

Here, $\aleph_i(t), i = 1, 2, 3$, partition \mathbb{R}_+ into regions where $V(x(t))$ exceeds, falls below, or lies between the thresholds $\gamma_1 V(x(0))e^{-\eta t}$ and $\gamma_2 V(x(0))e^{-\eta t}$. These sets satisfy $\aleph_1(t) \cup \aleph_2(t) \cup \aleph_3(t) = \mathbb{R}_+$ for all t .

Obviously, the boundaries between $\aleph_1(t)$ and $\aleph_3(t)$, $\aleph_2(t)$ and $\aleph_3(t)$ are as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{B}_1(t) &:= \left\{ \nu \in \mathbb{R}_+ : \nu = \gamma_1 V(x(0))e^{-\eta(t-t_0)} \right\}, \\ \mathcal{B}_2(t) &:= \left\{ \nu \in \mathbb{R}_+ : \nu = \gamma_2 V(x(0))e^{-\eta(t-t_0)} \right\}.\end{aligned}$$

Then, based on condition (11) and $\alpha > \eta$, the following proof is similar to (Ding, Wang, & Zhang, 2019) and (Ding & Wang, 2020), and is therefore omitted. When $V(x(t_0)) \in \aleph_1(t_0)$, we have

$$V(x(t)) \leq \begin{cases} V(x(t_0))e^{-\alpha(t-t_0)}, & t_0 \leq t \leq t_1, \\ \gamma_1 V(x(t_0))e^{-\eta(t-t_0)}, & t \geq t_1. \end{cases}$$

When $V(x(t_0)) \in \aleph_2(t_0) \cup \aleph_3(t_0)$, we can get

$$V(x(t)) \leq \gamma_1 V(t_0)e^{-\eta(t-t_0)}, \quad t \geq t_0.$$

Based on the variation of the $V(x(t))$, it can be obtained that $\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \kappa \gamma_1 \|x(t_0)\| e^{-\eta(t-t_0)/2} = 0$. Therefore, the origin of system (1) is UGES under the EbIC (8) with data-based ETM (25)-(26). \square

Remark 3. The design of the EbIC strategy includes the computation of the control gain and the construction of the ETM to activate the controller on demand. Unfortunately, both parts of the existing results (Ding, Wang, & Zhang, 2019; Ding & Wang, 2020; Yan, Liu, Xiao, & Zhang, 2022) rely on constructed linear matrix inequalities containing known system matrices A, B . To overcome the model dependence problem, we find the control gain based on Φ calculated from the data-based condition (11). Subsequently, we establish the data-based ETM (25)-(26) by combining parameter Φ , data \mathcal{X}_0 , state information $x(t)$, and auxiliary functions $\xi(t), \omega(t)$. The ETM proposed by (De Persis, Postoyan, & Tesi, 2024) reduces control input updates through a single triggering rule, while the ETM (25)-(26) minimizes control time by alternately activating/deactivating triggers. The triggering rules (25) and (26) are applied to controlled and uncontrolled scenarios, respectively.

Example 2: We consider the same system parameter settings as in Example 1. Data-driven EbIC and system-identification-based methods correspond to the following two situations:

Case 1 (Data-driven EbIC): We design the aperiodic intermittent controller (8) with ETM (25)-(26). The parameter of the auxiliary functions is set as $\eta = 0.45 < \alpha$, and their initial values are given by the data and $\gamma_1 = 1.2$, $\gamma_2 = 0.6$. Solving the data-based condition (11) to obtain the feedback gain matrix $K = [-7.5172, -0.6050, -17.4899, -8.3782]$. The ETM (25)-(26) can be designed from the solved Φ and the dataset.

Case 2 (System-identification-based EbIC): Based on the matrices A_s and B_s identified in Example 1, we solve for the parameter P using conditions (16) and (21), where $K = -B_s^T P$. Then, we design the control gain $K = [1.5172, -6.6050, 0.4899, -0.8782]$ and the ETM (29)-(30).

The trajectories $x(t)$ of the two methods are shown in Figure 2. The control costs $\int_0^{30} u^T(t)u(t)dt$ for the two methods are $4.5282 * 10^4$ and $1.0850 * 10^5$, respectively. This indicates that the ETM, designed directly based on data, not only enables the system to converge faster but also reduces control costs. Additionally, EbIC is more cost-effective than TbIC.

Figure 2. Trajectories $x(t)$ of the system (1) under two cases

5. Data-driven intermittent control with zero-order-hold updates

The intermittent controllers designed in Sections 3 and 4 are continuously updated in the control interval $[t_\sigma, t_\sigma + \Delta_\sigma)$, which also consumes a amount of control resources. To further minimize the control costs, based on the idea of sampled-data control (Ni, Wang, Huang, Ma, & Shen, 2022; Yu, Jiang, & Hu, 2017; Zhao & Hua, 2021) and event-triggered control (Wu, Guo, Xue, Ahn, & Liu, 2024; Wu, Wang, Liu, & Xu, 2021; Guo, Duan, & Wang, 2022), we design the following intermittent controller with

zero-order-hold updates to reduce the controller update frequency,

$$u(t) = \begin{cases} cKx(t_\sigma), & t \in [t_\sigma, t_\sigma + \Delta_\sigma), \\ 0, & t \in [t_\sigma + \Delta_\sigma, t_{\sigma+1}), \end{cases} \quad (36)$$

where $c > 0$ is a control gain, and is specified later. $\{t_\sigma\}_{\sigma=0}^\infty$ is both a control starting sequence and a sampling time sequence.

Next, we consider data-driven TbIC and EbIC with discrete controller updates, respectively.

5.1. Data-driven TbIC with zero-order-hold updates

We first give results for A-TbIC with zero-order-hold updates based on Theorem 1. It should be noted that this section requires constraints on subintervals based on Assumption 4 in order to achieve the UGES of system (1).

Theorem 3. Consider the linear system (1). Suppose Assumptions 1,2,4 hold. If there exist matrix Φ , and positive scalars $\alpha, \beta, c, \varepsilon$ such that (11) and

$$\begin{bmatrix} \Upsilon\Phi + (\Upsilon\Phi)^T - \mathcal{X}_0\Phi + \varepsilon\Theta\Theta^T & \Phi^T \\ \Phi & -\varepsilon\lambda_z^{-1}I \end{bmatrix} \prec 0, \quad (37)$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} \Upsilon\Phi + (\Upsilon\Phi)^T - \varepsilon\Theta\Theta^T & \Phi^T \\ \Phi & \varepsilon\lambda_z^{-1}I \end{bmatrix} \succ 0, \quad (38)$$

$$\bar{\alpha}\theta - \beta(1 - \theta) > 0, \quad (39)$$

where $\bar{\alpha} = \alpha - c^2e^{\alpha\varpi} > 0$ and $\bar{\Delta}$ and ϖ are defined in Assumption 4. Then, the origin of system (1) is UGES under the aperiodic intermittent controller (9) and (36).

Proof: Consider the $V(x)$ presented in Theorem 1. We will develop the stability analysis of the system (1) from the control and non-control intervals respectively.

(i) In this part, we will analyze the variation of the Lyapunov function in the control intervals. Condition (11) plays the same role as the Theorem 1.

For (37), using the Schur complement and Lemma 3 with $Y = -\Phi^T$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \Upsilon\Phi + (\Upsilon\Phi)^T + \varepsilon^{-1}\Phi^T\tilde{\Upsilon}^T\tilde{\Upsilon}\Phi + \varepsilon\Theta\Theta^T &\prec \mathcal{X}_0\Phi \\ \Upsilon\Phi + (\Upsilon\Phi)^T - \mathcal{W}\tilde{\Upsilon}\Phi - (\mathcal{W}\tilde{\Upsilon}\Phi)^T &\prec \mathcal{X}_0\Phi \\ (\mathcal{X}_1 - \mathcal{W})\tilde{\Upsilon}\Phi + [(\mathcal{X}_1 - \mathcal{W})\tilde{\Upsilon}\Phi]^T &\prec \mathcal{X}_0\Phi. \end{aligned}$$

Note that $\tilde{\Upsilon} = Z\Pi\Pi U$ and $(\mathcal{X}_1 - \mathcal{W})L = BK$, we get

$$\begin{aligned} (\mathcal{X}_1 - \mathcal{W})L + (\mathcal{X}_1 - \mathcal{W})^T L &\prec P^{-1}, \\ \Gamma + \Gamma^T &\prec P, \end{aligned} \quad (40)$$

where $\Gamma = PBK$.

Similar to (37), it can be derived from (38) that

$$\Upsilon\Phi + (\Upsilon\Phi)^T - \varepsilon^{-1}\Phi^T\tilde{\Upsilon}^T\tilde{\Upsilon}\Phi - \varepsilon\Theta\Theta^T \succ 0.$$

By applying Lemma 3 with $S = \Phi^T$, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} & \Upsilon\Phi + (\Upsilon\Phi)^T - \mathcal{W}\tilde{\Upsilon}\Phi - (\mathcal{W}\tilde{\Upsilon}\Phi)^T \succ 0 \\ & (\mathcal{X}_1 - \mathcal{W})\tilde{\Upsilon}\Phi + [(\mathcal{X}_1 - \mathcal{W})\tilde{\Upsilon}\Phi]^T \succ 0 \\ & \Gamma + \Gamma^T \succ 0. \end{aligned} \tag{41}$$

When $t \in [t_\sigma, t_\sigma + \Delta_\sigma)$, combined with (11), (40), and (41), we can obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{V}(x(t)) &= x^T(t)(PA + A^T P)x(t) + cx^T(t_\sigma)\Gamma x(t) \\ &\quad + cx^T(t)\Gamma^T x(t_\sigma) \\ &= x^T(t)(PA + A^T P)x(t) - \\ &\quad [-cx^T(t)\Gamma x(t_\sigma) - cx^T(t_\sigma)\Gamma^T x(t) \\ &\quad + \frac{1}{2}x^T(t)\Gamma x(t) + \frac{1}{2}x^T(t)\Gamma^T x(t) \\ &\quad + \frac{c^2}{2}x^T(t_\sigma)\Gamma x(t_\sigma) + \frac{c^2}{2}x^T(t_\sigma)\Gamma^T x(t_\sigma)] + \\ &\quad + \frac{1}{2}x^T(t)\Gamma x(t) + \frac{1}{2}x^T(t)\Gamma^T x(t) \\ &\quad + \frac{c^2}{2}x^T(t_\sigma)\Gamma x(t_\sigma) + \frac{c^2}{2}x^T(t_\sigma)\Gamma^T x(t_\sigma) \\ &\leq x^T(t)(PA + A^T P)x(t) + \frac{1}{2}x^T(t)\Gamma x(t) \\ &\quad + \frac{c^2}{2}x^T(t_\sigma)\Gamma x(t_\sigma) + \frac{1}{2}x^T(t)\Gamma^T x(t) \\ &\quad + \frac{c^2}{2}x^T(t_\sigma)\Gamma^T x(t_\sigma) \\ &\leq x^T(t)(PA + A^T P)x(t) + x^T(t)(\Gamma + \Gamma^T)x(t) \\ &\quad + c^2x^T(t_\sigma)(\Gamma + \Gamma^T)x(t_\sigma) \\ &\leq -\alpha V(x(t)) + c^2V(x(t_\sigma)). \end{aligned} \tag{42}$$

In what follows, we will estimate the upper bound of $V(x(t))$. The following systems are considered

$$\dot{\Upsilon}(t) = -\alpha\Upsilon(t), \quad \Upsilon(t_\sigma) = V(x(t_\sigma)), \quad t \in [t_\sigma, t_\sigma + \Delta_\sigma). \tag{43}$$

Due to $c^2V(x(t_\sigma)) > 0$, according to the comparison principle, it is straightforward to observe that $V(x(t)) > \Upsilon(t)$ for all $t > t_\sigma$. It can be obtained from (43) that

$$\Upsilon(t) = e^{-\alpha(t-t_\sigma)}\Upsilon(t_\sigma).$$

Therefore, $V(x(t)) \geq \Upsilon(t) = e^{-\alpha(t-t_\sigma)}\Upsilon(t_\sigma)$, which further means that

$$V(x(t_\sigma)) \leq e^{\alpha(t-t_\sigma)}V(x(t)) \leq e^{\alpha\varpi}V(x(t)). \quad (44)$$

From (44), one has for $t \in [t_\sigma, t_\sigma + \Delta_\sigma)$

$$\dot{V}(x(t)) \leq (-\alpha + c^2e^{\alpha\varpi})V(x(t)) \leq -\bar{\alpha}V(x(t)),$$

where $\bar{\alpha} = \alpha - c^2e^{\alpha\varpi}$ and then

$$V(x(t)) \leq V(x(t_\sigma))e^{-\bar{\alpha}(t-t_\sigma)}. \quad (45)$$

It can be obtained from (45) that

$$\begin{cases} V(x(t)) \leq V(x(t_\sigma))e^{-\bar{\alpha}(t-t_\sigma)}, \\ V(x(t_\sigma + \Delta_\sigma)) \leq V(x(t_\sigma))e^{-\bar{\alpha}\Delta_\sigma}. \end{cases} \quad (46)$$

(ii) Similar to part (ii) of Theorem 1, when $t \in [t_\sigma + \Delta_\sigma, t_{\sigma+1})$, it is easy to obtain

$$\begin{cases} V(x(t)) \leq V(x(t_\sigma + \Delta_\sigma))e^{\beta(t-t_\sigma-\Delta_\sigma)}, \\ V(x(t_{\sigma+1})) \leq V(x(t_\sigma))e^{\beta(t_{\sigma+1}-t_\sigma-\Delta_\sigma)-\bar{\alpha}\Delta_\sigma}. \end{cases} \quad (47)$$

Based on (46), (47), and Assumption 4, for $\forall \sigma \in \mathbb{N}$, one has

$$\begin{aligned} V(x(t_{\sigma+1})) &\leq V(t_0) e^{\sum_{q=0}^{\sigma} \beta(t_{q+1}-t_q-\Delta_q)-\bar{\alpha}\Delta_\sigma} \\ &\leq V(x(t_0))e^{(-\bar{\alpha}\bar{\Delta}+\beta(\varpi-\bar{\Delta}))(\sigma+1)}. \end{aligned}$$

According to (39), we have $\lim_{\sigma \rightarrow \infty} V(t_\sigma) = 0$. Therefore, the origin of system (1) is UGES under the A-TbIC (36) with feedback gain K computed from (11) and (37)-(39). \square

5.2. Data-driven EbIC with zero-order-hold updates

To realize the EbIC strategy with zero-order-hold updates, a hybrid ETM is designed as follows

$$t_{\sigma+1} = \inf \left\{ t > t_\sigma + \hat{\Delta} \mid \bar{h}(x, t) > 0 \right\}, \quad (48)$$

where the initial triggering instant is defined as $t_0 = 0$, the period $\hat{\Delta} > \Delta_\sigma$ is a designed constant and triggering function $\bar{h}(x, t)$ is designed later.

The measurement error of the system (1) can be expressed as $e(t) := x(t_\sigma) - x(t)$. The data-based triggering function $\bar{h}(x, t)$ is designed as

$$\bar{h}(t) = e^T(t)\Lambda_1 e(t) - \psi x^T(t_\sigma)\Lambda_2 x(t_\sigma), \quad (49)$$

where Λ_1 and Λ_2 are matrices designed from data (3), and ψ is a positive constant to be determined.

Applying the controller (36) to the system (1) yields

$$\begin{cases} \dot{x}(t) = Ax(t) + cBK e(t) + cBK x(t), \\ \qquad \qquad \qquad t \in [t_\sigma, t_\sigma + \Delta_\sigma), \end{cases} \quad (50a)$$

$$\begin{cases} \dot{x}(t) = Ax(t), \\ \qquad \qquad \qquad t \in [t_\sigma + \Delta_\sigma, t_{\sigma+1}). \end{cases} \quad (50b)$$

Theorem 4. Consider the system (1). Suppose Assumptions 1-2 hold. If there exist matrices Φ , Λ_1 , Λ_2 , and positive scalars α , β , c , ε such that (11), (38), and

$$\begin{bmatrix} \Upsilon\Phi + (\Upsilon\Phi)^T - \Lambda_1 + \varepsilon\Theta\Theta^T & \Phi^T \\ \Phi & -\varepsilon\lambda_z^{-1}I \end{bmatrix} \prec 0, \quad (51)$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} \Upsilon\Phi + (\Upsilon\Phi)^T - \Lambda_2 - \varepsilon\Theta\Theta^T & \Phi^T \\ \Phi & \varepsilon\lambda_z^{-1}I \end{bmatrix} \succ 0, \quad (52)$$

where $\zeta = \frac{2c\psi}{1-2\psi} + 2c < 1$ and $0 < \psi < \frac{1}{2}$. Then, the origin of system (1) is UGES under the intermittent controller (9), (36), and the hybrid ETM (48).

Proof: (i) In this part, we will analyze the variation of the Lyapunov function in the control intervals. Similar to part (i) of Theorem 3, from (51) and (52), it follows that

$$\begin{aligned} \Upsilon\Phi + (\Upsilon\Phi)^T + \varepsilon^{-1}\Phi^T\tilde{\Upsilon}^T\tilde{\Upsilon}\Phi + \varepsilon\Theta\Theta^T &\prec \Lambda_1, \\ (\mathcal{X}_1 - \mathcal{W})L + (\mathcal{X}_1 - \mathcal{W})^T L &\prec \Lambda_1 \\ PBK + (PB)^T K &\prec \Lambda_1, \end{aligned} \quad (53)$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} \Upsilon\Phi + (\Upsilon\Phi)^T - \varepsilon^{-1}\Phi^T\tilde{\Upsilon}^T\tilde{\Upsilon}\Phi - \varepsilon\Theta\Theta^T &\succ \Lambda_2, \\ (\mathcal{X}_1 - \mathcal{W})L + (\mathcal{X}_1 - \mathcal{W})^T L &\succ \Lambda_2, \\ PBK + (PB)^T K &\succ \Lambda_2. \end{aligned} \quad (54)$$

When $t \in [t_\sigma, t_\sigma + \Delta_\sigma)$, differentiating $V(x)$ along the system (50), one has

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{V}(x(t)) &= x^T(t)(PA + A^T P)x(t) + cx^T(t)(\Gamma + \Gamma^T)x(t) \\ &\quad + cx^T(t)\Gamma e(t) + ce^T(t)\Gamma^T x(t) \\ &\leq x^T(t)(PA + A^T P)x(t) + 2cx^T(t)(\Gamma + \Gamma^T)x(t) \\ &\quad + ce^T(t)(\Gamma + \Gamma^T)e(t). \end{aligned} \quad (55)$$

According to the (38), (49), (53), (54), and $\psi < \frac{1}{2}$, it can be verified that

$$\begin{aligned}
e^T(t)\Lambda_1 e(t) &\leq \psi x(t_\sigma)^T \Lambda_2 x(t_\sigma) \\
&\leq 2\psi e^T(t)\Lambda_2 e(t) + 2\psi x^T(t)\Lambda_2 x(t), \\
e^T(t)\Lambda_1 e(t) &\leq \frac{2\psi}{1-2\psi} x^T(t)\Lambda_2 x(t), \\
e^T(t)(\Gamma + \Gamma^T)e(t) &< \frac{2\psi}{1-2\psi} x^T(t)(\Gamma + \Gamma^T)x(t).
\end{aligned} \tag{56}$$

Noticing that $\zeta < 1$, substituting (56) into (55), we arrive at

$$\begin{aligned}
\dot{V}(x(t)) &\leq x^T(t)(PA + A^T P)x(t) + 2cx^T(t)(\Gamma + \Gamma^T)x(t) \\
&\quad + ce^T(t)(\Gamma + \Gamma^T)e(t) \\
&\leq x^T(t)(PA + A^T P)x(t) \\
&\quad + (2c + c\frac{2\psi}{1-2\psi})x^T(t)(\Gamma + \Gamma^T)x(t) \\
&\leq x^T(t)(PA + A^T P + \Gamma + \Gamma^T)x(t) \\
&\leq -\alpha V(x(t)).
\end{aligned} \tag{57}$$

Therefore, when $t \in [t_\sigma, t_\sigma + \Delta_\sigma)$, we have

$$\begin{cases} V(x(t)) \leq V(t_\sigma) e^{-\alpha(t-t_\sigma)}, \\ V(x(t_\sigma + \Delta_\sigma)) \leq V(x(t_\sigma)) e^{-\alpha\Delta_\sigma}. \end{cases} \tag{58}$$

(ii) Similar to part (ii) of Theorem 1, when $t \in [t_\sigma + \Delta_\sigma, t_{\sigma+1})$, it is easy to obtain

$$\begin{cases} V(x(t)) \leq V(x(t_\sigma + \Delta_\sigma)) e^{\beta(t-t_\sigma-\Delta_\sigma)}, \\ V(x(t_{\sigma+1})) \leq V(x(t_\sigma)) e^{\beta(t_{\sigma+1}-t_\sigma-\Delta_\sigma)-\alpha\Delta_\sigma}. \end{cases} \tag{59}$$

For $\forall \sigma \in \mathbb{N}$, using the iteration method, it can be obtained from (58) and (59)

$$V(x(t_{\sigma+1})) \leq V(x(t_0)) e^{\sum_{q=0}^{\sigma} \beta(t_{q+1}-t_q-\Delta_q)-\alpha\Delta_q}.$$

Since $(t_{\sigma+1}-t_\sigma)/\Delta_\sigma < \alpha/\beta+1$, this implies that $\lim_{\sigma \rightarrow \infty} \sum_{q=0}^{\sigma} \{\beta(t_{q+1}-t_q-\Delta_q)-\alpha\Delta_q\} = -\infty$. Therefore, the origin of system (1) is UGES stabilized under the EbIC (36) with hybrid ETM (48). \square

Remark 4. The TbIC and EbIC in this section update the control inputs only at the control starting moment t_σ , not continuously throughout the time intervals $[t_\sigma, t_\sigma + \Delta_\sigma)$. Specifically, the information $x(t_\sigma)$ is used instead of $x(t)$ in the control interval. Therefore, the proposed controller (36) not only reduces the control time, but also resembles a data-based event-triggered controller (De Persis, Postoyan, & Tesi, 2024) that is able to decrease the number of controller updates.

This example gives results for TbIC and EbIC strategies with zero-order-hold updates in Theorems 3 and 4.

Example 3: We consider the same system parameter settings as in Examples 1 and 2. Theorems 3, 4 and their corresponding system-identification-based methods

correspond to the following four cases, respectively.

Case 1 (Data-driven TbIC with zero-order-hold updates): The parameters are the same as in Example 1. Solving the data-based conditions (11) and (37)-(39) to obtain the feedback gain matrix $K = [-5.342, -0.1717, -6.3204, -11.0712]$.

Case 2 (System-identification-based TbIC with zero-order-hold updates): Based on the matrices A_s and B_s , we solve for the parameter P using conditions (16), (21), (40), and (41), where $K = -B_s^T P$. Then, we obtain the control gain $K = [-3.1346, -1.1014, 0.8316, -7.3083]$.

Case 3 (Data-driven EbIC with zero-order-hold updates): We design the intermittent controller (36) with hybrid ETM (48) based on Theorem 4. The parameters are set as $\psi = 0.25$, $\hat{\Delta} = \Delta_\sigma = 0.2$. Solving the data-based conditions (11), (38), (51), and (52) to obtain the feedback gain matrix $K = [-6.1102, 0.0319, -4.3373, -9.0227]$.

Case 4 (System-identification-based EbIC with zero-order-hold updates): Based on the matrices A_s and B_s , we solve for the parameter P using conditions (16), (21), (53), and (54), where $K = -B_s^T P$. Then, we obtain the control gain $K = [-4.7234, -0.0034, -1.8291, -5.0328]$.

The trajectories $x(t)$ of the system (1) under four cases are shown in Figure 3. Their control costs $\int_0^{30} u^T(t)u(t)dt$ are 3.2831×10^5 , 6.0078×10^5 , 1.0950×10^5 , and 1.9276×10^5 , respectively. Their controller update numbers are 28, 28, 19, and 23. Obviously, TbIC and EbIC, which use direct data-driven methods, have faster convergence rates and lower control costs than those based on system identification. Additionally, compared to Examples 1 and 2, the update numbers are significantly reduced.

Figure 3. Trajectories $x(t)$ of the system (1) under four cases.

6. Conclusions

This paper has proposed a direct data-driven intermittent control strategy for tackling the stabilization problem of unknown linear systems. To save control costs, we

have developed aperiodic TbIC and characterized the control gain and control interval ratio directly using noisy data. To further reduce the control time, EbIC has been considered, featuring an ETM designed directly from noisy data. In addition, a discrete updating scheme has been incorporated into both TbIC and EbIC. Simulation results demonstrate that the proposed strategies have effectively stabilized unknown linear systems, and compared with system-identification-based methods, these strategies have exhibited a faster convergence rate and lower control cost.

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